

Assessment of mammals diversity in Daphar forest, Mandi Bahauddin, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

In the present study, the diversity of mammals is studied in the vicinity of Daphar forest, district Mandi Bahauddin, “Punjab”, Pakistan. A total of 20 species are recorded, which belong to 16 genera, 13 families, and 7 orders from the Daphar forest. The majority of mammalian species belong to the orders Rodentia and Carnivora, followed by Eulipotyphla, Artiodactyla, Eulipotyphla, Pholidota, and Lagomorpha. Diversity indices are noted as: the Shanon-wiener diversity index is 1.14253, the richness is 6.871801 and the evenness is 0.878173. The Asiatic jackal is documented as the most abundant species in the Daphar forest. Indicated Indian pangolin, chinkara, and small Indian civet are observed in Daphar forest, and are declining. Several mammalian species are habitat-specific; hence corridors and linkages across diverse landscapes are required for mammalian variety conservation. The current study indicates local communities' broad knowledge and close ties to mammalian species, which could benefit in the sustainable use of the area's diversity.

Key words: Mammals, Diversity, Richness, Evenness, Daphar forest, Pakistan

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INTRODUCTION

In the world, total species of mammals are 5,416 including 29 orders and 154 families which have been taken under observation according to the study of the researchers (Wilson *et al.*, 2006). Pakistan holds the exclusive and unique floral and faunal variety. 195 species of mammalian species are present in country of Pakistan (Roberts, 2005b, a).

Biodiversity deals with the variety of of living organisms (Abbasi, 2021; Riaz and Altaf, 2021). It also deals with the protection of the ecosystem by practicing different measures in order to retain the survival of human being in the best possible way (Bilal *et al.*, 2021). Biodiversity changes significantly in different regions of the world and also act as bioindicator (Sidra *et al.*, 2019; Babar and Kanwal, 2021). The variety of different living organisms throughout the world rely on different climatic and weather conditions like soil, altitude, air, temperature, erosion, precipitation, weathering and geography of the specific area. According to the researchers, there is about one percent species of the world that is termed as existent species because of

ecosystem alteration which is also causing extermination (Raup, 1994; Maclaurin and Sterelny, 2008).

The most serious current environmental issue is the loss of biodiversity that is continuously challenging and threatening for the survival of human and precious ecosystem services (Barnosky *et al.*, 2012; Ijaz and Adil, 2021). In this era, the rates of extermination or extinction are about one thousand times greater than the previous (Ceballos *et al.*, 2017). The threatening wave of extinction spreads over one-fifth of all vertebrates (Hoffmann *et al.*, 2010). These points are kept in mind and planned this study; the major aim of the research is to know the diversity of mammals in “Daphar forest, Pakistan”.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The existing examination is carried out in “December 2017” to “Jun 2018” in Mandi Bahauddin District (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of the Daphar forest (PWFD, 2021).

STUDY AREA

The Daphar wildlife sanctuary is Reserved Forest having an area of 7135 acres. The Daphar forest is situated at the intersection of latitude 32 - 26° North and longitude 73 -11° East in the Malikwal Tehsil of Mandi Bahauddin District. The climatic conditions of Daphar forest are semi arid and subtropical type. The average temperature ranges from 10- 47°C and average annual rainfall of this forest is 0.2 to 7.24 inches throughout the year (Adil *et al.*, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The data collected from Daphar Plantation, Mandi Bahauddin. This “linear count” is utilized and diversity of mammals is documented by “direct” and “indirect counts”. The “direct count” includes “physical presence” alongwith “voices”; whereas “indirect count” includes body parts, hair mounting, waste material, patterns of feet, signs seen on plants, also the questionnaire conducted by people (Altaf, 2016; Haider and Altaf, 2018; Haidar, 2021). In order to observe the animals, binoculars (32x50) was used for study and accessed to accurate recognition of mammalian classes (Roberts, 2005b, a). The diversity comparison in different zones will aid in determining human impacts on the species of the area.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

“Shannon-Weiner index” ” i.e. H' (Shannon and Weaver, 1949) is utilized to document the diversity of various mammalian species;

$$“H' = - [\sum P_i \ln P_i]”$$

“Richness” (Margalef, 1958) is measured;

$$“R = S - 1 / \ln N”$$

“Evenness” (Pielou, 1966) is measured;

$$“E = H' / \ln (S)”$$

Where,

“ P_i ” = “Proportion of species relative to the total numeral of species”

While “ $\ln P_i$ ” = “Natural logarithm of this proportion”

Where “ S ” = “Total no. of species”

And “ N ” = “Total no. of individual”

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Total 20 species is recorded which belongs to 16 genera, 13 families (viz. Bovidae, Canidae, Erinaceidae, Felidae, Herpestidae, Hystricidae, Leporidae, Manidae, Muridae, Sciuridae, Soricidae, Suidae, and Viverridae) (see Figure 2) and 7 orders (viz. Carnivora, Eulipotyphla, Artiodactyla, Rodentia, Pholidota, Lagomorpha and Eulipotyphla) (Figure 3) from Daphar forest. Diversity indices are noted as; Shannon-wiener diversity index is 1.14253, Richness is 6.871801 and Evenness as 0.878173 (Table: 2).

In present study, “*Canis aureus*” is noted as topmost abundant species of present survey area and relative abundance (i.e. RA) is as 0.142611684, and the specific species is in the past observed from whole Pakistan (Roberts, 1997; Ghalib *et*

al., 2007; Rais *et al.*, 2011; Altaf *et al.*, 2014; Khan *et al.*, 2015; Iqbal *et al.*, 2018; Younus *et al.*, 2018; Rasheed *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 3: Orders of mammalian species documented in Daphar forest.

Figure 3: Orders of mammalian species documented in Daphar forest.

During research document that Jungle cat is present (RA = 0.04467354) in Daphar forest. The specific species is earlier documented from whole Pakistan

(Roberts, 1997; Rais *et al.*, 2011; Khan *et al.*, 2015). Indian desert cat (*Felis silvestris ornate*) is noted to be abundant in Chotiari Reservoir. Indian dessert cat is before observed from “Punjab” and “Sindh” (Roberts, 1997; Rais *et al.*, 2011; Khan *et al.*, 2015).

House shrew is verified from the Daphar forest and RA is as 0.128865979. The specific species is also observed from KPK, “Punjab”, and “Sindh” (Roberts, 1997; Awan *et al.*, 2004; Rais *et al.*, 2011; Altaf *et al.*, 2014; Khan *et al.*, 2015).

Mediterranean pygmy shrew is observed from Daphar forest and RA is as 0.020618557. The specific species is before observed from “Balochistan”, KPK, “Punjab” and “Sindh” (Roberts).

Gazella bennettii is noted (RA =0.012027491) from Daphar forest and the specific species is before observed from “Balochistan”, KPK, “Punjab” and “Sindh” (Roberts).

Rattus rattus is observed in Daphar forest (RA = 0.065292096), and The specific species is observed from “Balochistan”, KPK, “Punjab” and “Sindh” (Roberts, 1997; Altaf *et al.*, 2012; Altaf *et al.*, 2014; Iqbal *et al.*, 2018).

Nothern palm squirrel (*Funnambulus pennantii*) is noted in Daphar forest and RA is as 0.073883162. *F. pennantii* is before documented from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, “Punjab”, “Sindh” and “Balochistan”.

Hystrix indica is recorded (RA=0.109965636) from Daphar forest, and *H. indica* is before documented from Azad Jammu and Kashmir, “Balochistan”, KPK, “Punjab” and “Sindh” (Roberts, 1997; Maan and Chaudhry, 2001; Rais *et al.*, 2011; Altaf *et al.*, 2014; Khan *et al.*, 2015; Iqbal *et al.*, 2018; Safeer *et al.*, 2018; Rasheed *et al.*, 2020).

House mouse (*Mus musculus*) is seen (RA=0.08419244) from Daphar forest. The specific species also documented in previous literature from whole Pakistan (Roberts, 1997; Rais *et al.*, 2011; Altaf *et al.*, 2012; Altaf *et al.*, 2014; Iqbal *et al.*, 2018; Manzoor *et al.*, 2018).

Indian Grey mongoose (*Herpestes edwardsii*) is seen in Daphar forest and RA is 0.048109966. *H. edwardsii* is before observed from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, “Punjab”, “Sindh” and “Balochistan” (Roberts, 1997; Ghalib *et al.*, 2007; Rais *et al.*, 2011; Khan *et al.*, 2015; Iqbal *et al.*, 2018).

Small Indian mongoose (*Herpestes javanicus*) is observed (RA=0.104810997) from Daphar forest. *H. javanicus* is before observed from Azad Jammu and Kashmir, “Punjab”, “Sindh” and “Balochistan” (Roberts, 1997; Ghalib *et al.*, 2007; Altaf *et al.*, 2012; Altaf *et al.*, 2014; Khan *et al.*, 2015; Altaf *et al.*, 2018).

Manis crassicaudata and *Viverricula indica* are observed and both species are rare (RA=0.003436426) in Daphar forest, and The specific species is recorded by other researcher (Roberts, 1997; Khan *et al.*, 2015; Iftkhar *et al.*, 2018) from AJK, “Punjab” and “Sindh”.

Little Indian field mouse (*Mus booduga*) is documented (RA=0.017182131) in Daphar forest and the specific species is observed from AJK, “Balochistan”, “Punjab”, “Sindh” and KPK (Roberts, 1997).

Indian Wildboar (*Sus scrofa*) is noted from Daphar forest and “RA” is as 0.030927835. *S. scrofa* is before documented from AJK, “Punjab”, “Sindh” and KPK

(Roberts, 1997; Rais *et al.*, 2011; Altaf *et al.*, 2014; Chughtai *et al.*, 2018; Rasheed *et al.*, 2020).

Indian bush rat (*Gulanda ellioti*) is noted from Daphar forest and “RA” is as 0.006872852. *G. ellioti* is before documented by wildlife biologist (Roberts) from Azad Jammu and Kashmir, “Balochistan”, “Punjab”, “Sindh” and KPK.

Indian Desert Hare (*Lepus nigricollis dayanus*) is noted from Daphar forest and “Relative abundance” is as 0.006872852, and before document from “Punjab”, “Sindh” and KPK (Roberts, 1997; Altaf *et al.*, 2014; Khan *et al.*, 2015; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018).

Long-eared desert hedgehog (*Hemiechinus collaris*) and Brandt's hedgehog (*Hemiechinus hypomelas*) are documented from Daphar forest and RA of both species are as; 0.017182131 and 0.008591065 respectively. *H. collaris* is before observed from AJK, “Punjab”, “Sindh” and KPK (Roberts, 1997; Altaf *et al.*, 2017) and *H. hypomelas* is before observed from whole Pakistan (Roberts, 1997; Ghalib *et al.*, 2007).

Diversity measurements of different habitat types indicate that the various types of habitats showing their effects in many ways on diversity of mammals in a specific habitat. Response of mammals is quick to human effects that cause extinction in many mammals. The number of species increases by giving moderate places for moderate urbanization, to some extent. Despite this, in the densely populated areas, the elimination of natural vegetation has reduced the number of biodiversity and thickness reduction. Urban development has produced some of the largest local extinction rates and often removed most native species.

Table 1: The diversity of the mammalian fauna of Dapher Forest of District Mandi Bahauddin “Punjab”- Pakistan

Sr.	Name Order, Family	Status	Pi/RA	LogPI	PiLogPi
1	Jungle cat <i>Felis chaus</i> (Schreber, 1777) Carnivora, Felidae	LC	0.04467354	-1.34995	-0.06031
2	Indian Desert Cat <i>Felis silvestris ornate</i> (Gray, 1832) Carnivora, Felidae	LC	0.037800687	-1.4225	-0.05377
3	House shrew <i>Suncus murinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766) Eulipotyphla, Soricidae	LC	0.128865979	-0.88986	-0.11467
4	Mediterranean pygmy shrew <i>Suncus etruscus</i> (Savi, 1822) Eulipotyphla, Soricidae	LC	0.020618557	-1.68574	-0.03476
5	Chinkara <i>Gazella bennettii</i> (Sykes, 1831) Artiodactyla, Bovidae	LC	0.012027491	-1.91982	-0.02309

6	House rat <i>Rattus rattus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Rodentia, Muridae	LC	0.065292096	-1.18514	-0.07738
7	Nothern palm squirrel <i>Funambulus pennantii</i> (Wroughton, 1905) Rodentia, Scuridae	LC	0.073883162	-1.13145	-0.0836
8	Indian Crested Porcupine <i>Hystrix indica</i> (Kerr, 1792) Rodentia, Hystricidae	LC	0.109965636	-0.95874	-0.10543
9	House mouse <i>Mus musculus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Rodentia, Muridae	LC	0.08419244	-1.07473	-0.09048
10	Indian Grey mongoose <i>Herpestes edwardsii</i> (É. Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1818) Carnivora, Herpestidae	LC	0.048109966	-1.31776	-0.0634
11	Small Indian mongoose <i>Herpestes javanicus</i> (É. Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1818) Carnivora, Herpestidae	LC	0.104810997	-0.97959	-0.10267
12	Indian Pangolin <i>Manis crassicaudata</i> (É. Geoffroy, 1803) Pholidota, Manidae	LC	0.003436426	-2.46389	-0.00847
13	Asiatic jackal <i>Canis aureus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Carnivora, Canidae	LC	0.142611684	-0.84584	-0.12063
14	Little Indian field mouse <i>Mus booduga</i> (Gray , 1837) Rodentia, Muridae	LC	0.017182131	-1.76492	-0.03033
15	Small Indian civet <i>Viverricula indica</i> (Hodgson, 1838) Carnivora, Viverridae	LC	0.003436426	-2.46389	-0.00847
16	Indian Wild boar <i>Sus scrofa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) Artiodactyla, Suidae	LC	0.030927835	-1.50965	-0.04669
17	Indian bush rat <i>Gulanda ellioti</i> (Gray, 1837) Rodentia, Muridae	LC	0.006872852	-2.16286	-0.01487

18	Indian Desert Hare <i>Lepus nigricollis dayanus</i> (F.Cuvier, 1823) Lagomorpha, Leporidae	LC	0.0395189	-1.4032	-0.05545
19	Long-eared desert hedgehog <i>Hemiechinus collaris</i> (Gray, 1830) Eulipotyphla, Erinaceidae	LC	0.017182131	-1.76492	-0.03033
20	Brandt's hedgehog <i>Hemiechinus hypomelas</i> (Brandt, 1836) Eulipotyphla, Erinaceidae	LC	0.008591065	-2.06595	-0.01775
H= - [ΣPi ln Pi]			1.14253		
R= S-1/LogN			6.871801		
E= H'/ln (S)			0.878173		

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